

**CHANGE
MAKERS**
EMERGING EXPERIENCE FOR YOUTH

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pedagogical and didactical guidelines_

HANDBOOK

SUMMARY

1.	INTRODUCTORY NOTE	3
2.	PROJECT DESCRIPTION	3
3.	THE FRAMEWORK APPROACHES	4
4.	ABOUT PLATFORM COMMUNICATION TOOLS	5
5.	ACTIVE LEARNING METHODOLOGIES	6
6.	POTENTIAL RISK AND BARRIERS BOTH WITHIN THE CREATION OF OPEN EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES, AND DURING THEIR USAGE IN THE DIGITAL COURSES	9
7.	ORGANIZATION OF LEARNING AND ASSESSMENT ENVIRONMENT	13
8.	BIBLIOGRAPHIC REFERENCES	14

1. INTRODUCTORY NOTE

This *Pedagogical and Didactical Guidelines* handbook is designed to project partners and target group under the “*ChangeMakers – Emerging Experience for Youth*” project to guide them through the project activities and bootcamps.

Designed specifically for project partners, who are likely organizations or individuals collaborating on the “*ChangeMakers*” project, the handbook aims to provide valuable support and direction throughout various project activities and bootcamps.

2. PROJECT DESCRIPTION

The project “*ChangeMakers – Emerging Experience for Youth*” developed an adapted framework that integrated a tailored learning toolkit to address a widespread challenge for young people: the transition from school to work. Since we identified this priority as an essential part of society and the impact that it has on young people, we aimed to:

1. share new learning methods and experiments by doing;
2. increase the community of youth for (either disadvantaged or not) for a safe, fair and accessible change;
3. boost values, skills, proficiency, and experience by learning in an immersive lifestyle ecosystem.

These were the main goals of our project. However, the project also raised awareness of this specific need since many young people did not have fair, accessible, and inclusive ways of shortening the gap between education and work. This gap is still full of challenges, questions, doubts, and lacks flexibility. In addition, there was also the competencies/skills spectrum in which many young people still fell short, particularly concerning valuable life skills (financial literacy, networking, communication, among others).

Shortly, the project provided the chance for these young people to have an active voice and participation in their choices. They had the possibility of being heard, and their actions had positive consequences. They are becoming more than a simple actor in society and shifting the parading where dynamic young people add value to diverse scenarios. The project framework implemented these critical aspects as core pillars and values, manifested in its activities, resources, models, methodologies, and solutions.

3. THE FRAMEWORK APPROACHES

Nowadays the teaching professionals could change of environment in a few hours, it was the lesson that we learn recently in 2020 year with the COVID'19 pandemic. Today teachers and students working face to face and tomorrow it's possible all of them go at home. Those rapidly changing demands require new competences, more flexibility in learning than before and more autonomy of students and teachers. Their roles change and it's necessary to change also the methodologies, the resources and the evaluation. The importance of digital competences of this public are mandatory to having success in this new normal that we live. The *European Framework for the Digital Competence of Educators (DigCompEdu)* is one the most important referential to describe and understand what means to be digitally competent. *DigCompEdu* have focus in innovative learning, in methodologies and integration of digital resources, details 22 competences organised in six different areas.

The XXI century educational challenges may be defined by the collaborative knowledge construction and the development of skills like research skills, digital literacy or civic and ethical literacy, and competences like problem solving, critical thinking, emotional intelligence or creativity and others.

Now, we will present some pedagogical approaches to facilitating Young People integration and with better impact on student learning. Those approaches are orientated to online learning and help to reflect about platform tools communication, integration of digital resources, learning methodologies (Project-Based Learning, Problem-Based Learning and Inquiry-Based Learning), evaluation methods (mandatory evaluation according to content and methodology like writing exam, oral exam, oral discussion project, evaluation portfolio or formative evaluation according to content and methodology: auto-evaluation, or peer to peer, learning portfolio, and problem solving activities like gaming).

4. ABOUT PLATFORM COMMUNICATION TOOLS

The way we work and learn has changed massively over the pandemic COVID-19. Now students learn and access information anytime, anywhere and on a variety of devices. Our learners expect highly-engaging, and up-to-date content that's readily available at their moment of need, because we don't know when we are able to be in face-to-face mode learning or in online learning.

The Berlin Declaration on Open Access to Knowledge in the Sciences and Humanities of 22 October 2003 "define open access as a comprehensive source of human knowledge and cultural heritage that has been approved by the scientific community (...) and accessible representation of knowledge. (...) Content and software tools must be openly accessible and compatible." in order to be flexible and adaptable by the user's community.

It's important to have some examples of those platforms:

4. Moodle is a learning management system platform designed to provide three levels of users: educators, administrators and learners with a single robust, secure and integrated system to create personalised learning environments. We can download the software into to a web server and do the configuration in order of our necessities.
5. The Microsoft Teams for education platform was created to help teachers and students at all stages of learning, as it allows for easy collaboration in real time, from organizing meetings on any device and having features designed to make students feel good. included, even when they are not in the classroom. This platform allows integration with some learning management systems such as Moodle.

Both of them have the possibility of communication in synchronous and asynchronous mode.

6. ZOOM Colibri platform is a web collaboration service that provides a suitable environment for holding classes, meetings and webinars for up to 300 remote participants. The platform allows you to easily conduct videoconferencing sessions with participants from multiple institutions, in a secure environment that includes management and probing tools, interaction, sharing and recording sessions.

All of those examples consider the possibility of share and publish internal and external resources in synchronous mode like videoconference, or in asynchronous mode like forum, glossary, wiki and others.

We have also the possibility to use Web 2.0 resources like H5P, Padlet, Mentimeter, Kahoot, Triceder, Google ARCore for new augmented reality learning experiences and some other educational tools.

5. ACTIVE LEARNING METHODOLOGIES

Project-Based Learning (PBL) students develop a research and design process aimed at finding the answer to a question. Currently, it's considered one of the most effective active methodologies implemented in educational systems and allows to learn in a flexible way. It also attributes a great level of importance to the knowledge construction process.

CHARACTERISTICS	BENEFITS	DISADVANTAGES
Through PBL, students develop a research and design process aimed at finding the answer to a question.	Allows the development of student independence	Number and size of working groups
Currently, it is considered one of the most effective active methodologies implemented in educational systems.	The entire course of the student is very focused on cooperation and collaboration tasks with peers.	Teacher preparation time
Allows learning to be flexible.	Develops basic and fundamental skills and abilities	Lack of classroom space
It attributes a great level of importance to the knowledge construction process.	It calls for high levels of student motivation.	Difficulty for a single teacher to manage all the learning of the groups.
Allows a high level of deepening of knowledge by the students.	This methodology can appear as a complement to other learning strategies.	Difficulties with technology (lack of resources or infrastructure)
Uses and calls for the development of core (fundamental) skills	Allows the development of student independence	Number and size of working groups
Through PBL, students develop a research and design process aimed at finding the answer to a question.	The entire course of the student is very focused on cooperation and collaboration tasks with peers.	Number and size of working groups

INTERVENTION STEP BY STEP

- Step 1.** Post a challenge or question and identify ideas.
Step 2. Build working groups (eventually define roles).
Step 3. Start of investigation: general survey, field collection, etc.
Step 4. Organizing, planning and exchanging ideas.
Step 5. Detailed and systematic research and collection of data.
Step 6. Analysis, synthesis and verification of information.
Step 7. Preparation of all information obtained in the form of results/conclusions.
Step 8. Design of the final product.
Step 9. Presenting the final product to the wider community.
Step 10. General reflection (in large group).
Step 11. Evaluation. Project.

CHARACTERISTICS	BENEFITS	DISADVANTAGES
Focus on the Learning Process	Learning through problem sets and contextualized situations,	Time-consuming: PBL requires a significant investment of time and effort from both students and instructors.
Small Group and Cooperative Learning	Build knowledge and develop skills such as critical thinking, problem solving, communication and assessment.	PBL requires skilled facilitation to ensure that students stay on track, follow the learning objectives, and don't get bogged down in irrelevant details.
Students are Responsible for their own Learning	Open-ended nature learning.	May not be suitable for all students, particularly those who prefer a more structured learning environment
Integration of Knowledge and Skills	Integrate knowledge from multiple disciplines: PBL is often interdisciplinary.	Instructors need to be able to guide discussions, ask appropriate questions, and provide feedback to their students.
Integration of Different Domains	Enhance critical thinking and problem-solving skills	PBL is focused on a single problem or case, it may not cover as much content as a traditional lecture-based course.
Assessment Challenges		Assessing student learning in PBL can be challenging, as it may be difficult to objectively evaluate the individual quality

	of student research, analysis, and problem-solving skills.
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STRATEGY
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Define/Identify the problem; 2. Explore students' prior knowledge related to the problem; 3. Identify what knowledge is necessary to learn to solve the problem 4. Investigate the problem and look for solutions ; 5. Evaluate possible solutions to the problem ; 6. Streamline group work (maximum five students) and independent research; 7. The groups define the “learning issues” that they think are raised by each new problem and decide how to divide the work in order to solve them; 8. Assessment is authentic (contextualized and integrated into learning activities) and based on performance.

6. POTENTIAL RISK AND BARRIERS BOTH WITHIN THE CREATION OF OPEN EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES, AND DURING THEIR USAGE IN THE DIGITAL COURSES

Administrative Structure: an eLearning program necessarily establishes partnerships between different units within the same institution or between different institutions, which can create a series of barriers related to cost accounting, revenue distribution, among others.

Organizational Change: organizations' resistance to change. Without eLearning as a vision shared by all and strategically planned, the process will become very slow and difficult.

Technical Infrastructures, it is known in advance that it is difficult to keep technical updates up to date and without prejudice to the institution, whether we are talking about hardware or software; the lack of technological literacy of professors and of the employees themselves to be able to design, develop materials and teach at a distance.

Social factors that relate to the quality of social interactions that the eLearning system adopted by the institution allows. We focus on the problem of isolation that stakeholders may feel. This isolation can be motivated by the lack of face-to-face contact between those involved in the training process; discomfort of student-centered activities and collaborative work, as they change the traditional classroom setting in which the teacher directs student learning; Good quality materials and courses that take into account the absence of the teacher and the student from a common physical space, as well as special attention to the evaluation of student results, are required recommendations.

Time and compensation are important for the success of the eLearning system since the time spent by the institution in preparing materials, in experimenting with technology and techniques is very large, often jeopardizing the profitability of the system itself, being necessary It is urgent to support this type of project.

The threat of technology is seen by some teachers as a factor of possible reduction in the number of teachers, so the adoption of technology in the institution is immediately seen as a threat. If a teacher is intimidated by technology, , he can compromise his authority as a professional who leads a group of learners, so any of these psychological factors can lead the teacher to feel that his safety at work is threatened.

Legality and security, attention is drawn to issues of legality, copyright, piracy, property rights, plagiarism and other problems linked to the increasing use of the Internet in distance learning.

Evaluation/Efficacy is the factor that stands out as special because it requires great rigor and effectiveness of the distance evaluation systems. Much remains to be studied in this matter, since

only an effective and credible assessment system can prove much of the effectiveness of distance learning.

Info-exclusion, insofar as there are still some (teachers and students) who do not have easy access to the means of communication via the WWW, or to hardware or software that can make it possible to follow a distance course. Therefore, issues related to universal access to technological means have to be resolved when implementing an eLearning system.

Factors linked to student support services, attention is drawn to some services that may be more difficult to provide at a distance, such as: student counselling, access to library services for research, consultation and requesting books, the social and financial support of the student, as well as the certification of the student's identity, that is, proof, for example in the case of exams, that the student enrolled is the same one who takes the tests.

There are several **barriers** that restrict an institutional project based on eLearning. Such barriers are not considered as insurmountable, but which, if not addressed by the institution from the beginning, will undoubtedly jeopardize its success.

These barriers start to be felt from the moment in which the current educational paradigm and the organization and management of the institution are questioned, which form a strong part of its identity. The structure that has always served the school community now proves to be inappropriate in the implementation of an eLearning system (Moore, 1994), and the internal pressures blocking change are felt with the implementation of the eLearning system. Such behaviours are understandable, since human beings create habits and ways to solve the problematic situations that arise. Human beings don't like to change without understanding, or without feeling, into what extent this change will bring him advantages.

It's important to refer that "The major problems are associated with organizational change, change of the faculty roles, and change in administrative structures. Here we desperately need all the ideas and all the leadership that can be assembled. The starting point is to expose the problems." (1994, p. 03) This position therefore supports the need not to leave out the administrative structure of the institution's reorganization process, which will prove to be as important as necessary for this process and on an equal footing with the curricular and pedagogical structure. Generally, institutions are what the human resources that work in them want them to be, they are the ones who support their functioning and "Without this support, distance education is at risk of becoming a peripheral activity, without commitment from or significance to the institution." (Marrs quoted in Galusha, 2004, p. 08).

New solutions will have to be found regarding, for example, access to online enrolment by students, means of payment, information, and administrative requirements, such as consulting grades, requesting diplomas or certificates and other information, or even access to research sources and bibliographic consultation, among other things that will give credibility and legitimacy to this type of teaching in the institution. In addition to the necessary solutions in this area, information and

decision support will also have to be effective and easily upgradeable in order to guarantee the efficiency of the service. At this point, the administrative aspects are linked with the technological aspects that should propose ergonomic and user-friendly solutions. The relevance of technological infrastructures in an eLearning system depends on the success of the adopted pedagogical models, the autonomy of its users, as well as the needs for technical support.

In this complex set that interconnects technical, pedagogical, social and functional aspects, the higher education institution has a decisive role, which is difficult when it places the implementation of an eLearning system in its objectives. The higher education institution will face a wide set of problems that according to Berge (2001), which will mostly be associated with the necessary organizational change, the change in operating rules and the fundamental change in administrative structures. The author also points out five stages of organizational maturity in the face of the implementation of an eLearning system that make barriers more fragile or stronger depending on the positioning of the institution in these stages. The first includes institutions that have never carried out activities linked to eLearning, the second includes institutions that have carried out occasional or sporadic eLearning activities. Thirdly, there are institutions that have the technical and human capacity to organize and implement eLearning activities if they are proposed, and in the fourth place there are institutions that have established and planned an eLearning implementation and development strategy, while in the fifth place will include institutions that have perfectly institutionalized eLearning in their daily practice.

Depending on the positioning of the institution in this scale of stages, the weight of the factors that will constitute the barriers to the implementation of the eLearning that we have been talking about will vary. Reviewing some authors who refer to these barriers, we could see that the way of classifying and grouping them into categories is diverse (Rezabeck (1999). Cegles (1998). Leggett and Persichitte (1998). Garland's (1993). Merriel et al (1992) cited in Muilenberg and Berge. 2001) however, all authors include aspects related to the necessary organizational changes of institutions, in such a way they are striking and important for the full integration of eLearning to take place within the institutions.

Let us then adopt a set of 10 factors that constitute a barrier to the implementation of eLearning in an institution and that Muilenberg and Berge (2001) pointed out in a study on obstacles to the implementation of eLearning.

According to the authors, such factors identify barriers linked to the administrative structure: an eLearning program necessarily establishes partnerships between different units within the same institution or between different institutions, which can create a series of barriers related to cost accounting, revenue distribution, among others. There are also organizational change factors that these the authors draw attention to, which are the resistance of organizations to change. Without eLearning as a vision shared by all and strategically planned, the process will become very slow and difficult. The questions related to technical infrastructures follow, as it is known in advance that it is

difficult to keep technical updates up to date and without losses in the institution, whether we are talking about hardware or software. However, the authors focus their attention on the lack of technological literacy of teachers and employees themselves to be able to design, develop materials and teach at a distance. Another of the factors mentioned presents concerns of a social nature and is related to the quality of social interactions that the eLearning system adopted by the institution allows. In this case, the authors focus on the problem of isolation that the actors may feel. This isolation can be motivated by the lack of face-to-face contact between those involved in the training process. They also warn of the discomfort of student-centered activities and collaborative work, as they change the traditional classroom setting in which the teacher directs student learning. Good quality materials and courses that take into account the absence of the teacher and the student from a common physical space, as well as special attention to the evaluation of student results, are recommendations that the authors leave behind.

The factors that link time and compensation are addressed by Mulenberg and Berge (2001) as being also extremely important for the success of the eLearning system, since the time spent by the institution in the preparation of materials, in the experimentation of technology and techniques is very large, often jeopardizing the profitability of the system itself, making it necessary and urgent to support this type of project, which according to the authors is not always the case.

The threat of technology is seen by some teachers as a possible factor in reducing the number of teachers, so the adoption of technology in the institution is immediately seen as a threat. If a teacher is intimidated by technology, according to the authors, it can compromise their authority as a professional who leads a group of learners, so any of these psychological factors can lead the teacher to feel that their safety at work is threatened.

Legality and security is the seventh factor that the authors address and make us to draw our attention to the issues of legality, copyright, piracy, property rights and other issues connected with the increasing use of the Internet in distance learning. Evaluation/Efficacy, on the other hand, is the factor that the authors dedicate par excellence and because it deserves special attention to the effectiveness of distance evaluation systems. Much remains to be studied in this matter, since only an effective and credible assessment system can prove much of the effectiveness of distance learning. Ninthly, the authors draw attention to the very current issue of info-exclusion, as there are still many (teachers and students) who do not have easy access to the means of communication via the WWW, or so little to hardware or software. that can make it possible to follow a distance course. Therefore, issues related to universal access to technological means have to be resolved when implementing an eLearning system.

Finally, they present the factors linked to student support services, drawing attention to some services that may be more difficult to ensure at a distance, such as: student counseling, access to library services for research, consultation and requisition. of books, the social and financial support of

the student as well as the certification of the student's identity, that is, proof, for example in the case of exams, that the student enrolled is the same one who takes the tests.

All these factors have a very important weight and, according to Muilenberg and Berge (2001), help to reduce or consolidate the barriers and obstacles to the implementation of an eLearning system in an institution, being able to place the institution in stage one or in stage five of organizational maturity. facing the implementation of an eLearning system.

7. ORGANIZATION OF LEARNING AND ASSESSMENT ENVIRONMENT

Creating an effective learning and assessment environment requires careful organization and planning. Here are some key steps to consider:

1. **Define your Learning Objectives:** Before you can create an effective learning environment, you need to know what you want your students to learn. Identify the key skills, knowledge, and competencies you want them to acquire and develop clear learning objectives that align with those goals.
2. **Choose Appropriate Assessment Methods:** Different types of learning objectives require different types of assessments. Consider the best ways to measure student learning, such as written exams, projects, presentations, or group discussions. Be sure to align your assessment methods with your learning objectives.
3. **Provide Clear Instructions:** Make sure your students understand exactly what they need to do in order to succeed in your course. Provide clear instructions for assignments, assessments, and any other course requirements.
4. **Use Technology to your Advantage:** There are many tools and resources available to help you create an effective learning environment, such as learning management systems, digital textbooks, and online collaboration tools. Choose the ones that align with your goals and make the most sense for your students.
5. **Create an Effective Feedback and Environment Support:** In order students effectively learning, they need to feel supported and encouraged. Create a positive and inclusive classroom culture that promotes collaboration, respect, and growth. And don't forget to have an effective mentoring to support them.

By following these steps, you can create a learning and assessment environment that is effective, engaging, and supportive of student success.

- ✓ Start with a banner or image that brings identity to the group.
- ✓ Introduce yourself with a video.

- ✓ Create an information space and a communication space in the discipline.
- ✓ Provide guidelines and work schedule.
- ✓ Explain how the course is organized and what is the duration time of the course and student effort.
- ✓ Identify the modules and dates.
- ✓ Arrange all modules in the same way. This doesn't to create disorientation.
- ✓ Provide resources for autonomous work and practical activities to regulate learning.
- ✓ Promote dialogue between student by student and students and teacher.
- ✓ Promote dialogue, discussion and the sharing of resources, knowledge and work among students.
- ✓ Evaluate the students' satisfaction with the learning environment, with the resources and methodologies followed. Ask for improvement suggestions.

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